

A Study of Streaming Videos as a Substitute of Traditional Mode of Entertainment with Special Reference to Youth of Agra

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Abstract

There was a time when for getting access to quality television programming cable was considered the best source but nowadays online videos and streaming services are much more popular than they are a big threat to the existence of cable and satellite television. The internet TV apps are updating the quality very frequently and improvements take place at a quicker pace, promising an amazing video experience to the viewers. Data collection is based on a primary study through a questionnaire to provide a more accurate response as it is a kind of direct interaction with respondents and Analysis of data by MS-Excel tools and representation of it through Tables and graphs. This research paper is based on the responses of a particular age group (i.e. Youth 18-35 years) to examine their responses toward Streaming videos as a substitute of the traditional mode of entertainment and they belong to a particular city Agra, Uttar Pradesh, India

Keywords – Entertainment, Internet, Streaming Videos, Substitute, and Youth.

Introduction

There was a time when the sole means of getting access to quality television programming was Cable. The Availability of online video and Streaming Services is a kind of threat to cable and satellite television. The Improvement and updates to the quality of internet TV apps are taking place at a faster pace which in assuring an amazing video experience for the viewers. When it is to Streaming video, A process takes place which sent the content in compressed form over the Internet and the viewer displayed it in real-time. Downloading a file to play is not a problem with Streaming Video or Streaming

Media. Instead, media is played as it arrives because it is sent in a continuous stream of data. The user needs a player to uncompress and sent video data to display and audio data to speakers. We can download a player from the software maker's website or it can be an integral part of a browser. The expected growth of the Indian video-streaming market is \$700 million to \$2.4 billion by 2023.

Of 125 Respondents 20.8 % (26) are female and 79.2% (99) are male.

What is the highest level of education you have completed?
 125 responses

All respondents are Educated. Their highest level of education is like 33.6% respondents are graduates, 20.8% respondents are Postgraduates, 20.8% respondents are

undergraduate, 13.6% are High School Pass, 9.6% have 12th or equivalent and 1.6% opt for others.

Occupation
 125 responses

66 respondents out of 125 are students, 21 respondents are employed, 24 respondents are self-employed, 11 respondents are

unemployed, 2 respondents are housewives and 1 respondent is engaged in business.

Q1- Are you aware about concept of Streaming videos?
 125 responses

86.4% (108) respondents are aware of the concept of Streaming Videos whereas 13.6% (17) respondents are not

aware of the concept of Streaming Videos.

Q2- Do you like watching Streaming videos?
 125 responses

106 respondents out of 125 like watching Streaming Videos whereas 19 respondents do not like watching Streaming Videos.

Q3-Which one do you prefer more?
125 responses

Amazon Prime is most preferred Streaming Video Platform (59.2%) followed by Hotstar (55.2%), Netflix (53.6%), YouTube (1.6%) and

Zee5 (0.8%). (Total is more than 100% because one respondent responded for more than one option).

Q4- Which kind of content do you prefer to watch?
125 responses

Comedy is Most Preferred Content (49.6%) followed by Horror (41.6%), thriller (40%), Miscellaneous (29.6%) and Sensual/Erotic (24.8%). (Total is more than 100% because one respondent responded for more than one option).

favorite series which are as Mirzapur, Money Heist, The Family man , Patal Lok, Panchayat, Asur, The last Kingdom, the walking dead, better call Saul and stranger things, Vampire Diaries, the visions, lucifer, squid game, Game of Thrones, FRIENDS, 13 reasons why, Big Bang theory, Sherlock Holmes, two and a half men, Breaking bad, Sacred games , gullak, kota factory and so many.

Q5- Which are your favorite series? (Name any four)125 responses

17 respondents do not have any particular Favorite series while 108 respondents have

Q6- Does watching Streaming videos affect your behaviour?(If yes ,how)

125 responses

The behavior of 66 respondents out of 125 do not get affected by watching Streaming Videos whereas 59 respondents get affected, some in a positive way and some in a

negative way. positive changes contain a change in the way of learning, try to imitate their favorite characters, all videos are not only entertaining. Some are hidden message

to sharpen the thinking abilities, Influence thinking, randomly use some dialogues in day to day life what have heard in the near to last web series, build personality aspects, etc. and Negative changes contain Most of the web series on Netflix or any other streaming platform do portray the western culture, Be it the way they live, behave, what they wear

and eat, or feels superior and so it tempts to adopt the western culture, sometimes the content is too disturbing which forces the mind to think of those situations, it feels addictive and unproductive when we binge-watch but if we watch it for the lesser time it feels refreshing.

Q7- According to you are the charges of Streaming videos affordable?
 125 responses

According to 71.2% (89) respondents, Streaming Videos are affordable whereas according to 28.8% (36)

respondents, Streaming Videos are not Affordable.

Q8- Charges of which mode of entertainment are more affordable?

After summarizing the responses about the affordability of charges, Streaming Videos are more affordable followed by Cable T.V., Big Cinemas and DTH is the least affordable. The reason behind

it could be that some platform provides streaming videos for free whereas DTH and Cable T.V. required a setup and Big Cinemas charge according per show.

Q9- Are Streaming videos better than T.V.?
 125 responses

35.2% of respondents agree with the statement that Streaming Videos are better than T.V., 28% of respondents strongly agree, 26.4% of respondents neither agree nor disagree, 8.8% of

respondents disagree and 1.6% of respondents strongly disagree with the statement that Streaming Videos are better than T.V.

Q10-Does watching Streaming videos have any economic impact on you?(If yes,specify)
 125 responses

78 out of 125 respondents have no economic impact due to watching Streaming Videos whereas 47 respondents have an economic impact

as some platforms are costly or out of budget but due to addiction or a habit of watching videos have to purchase a subscription.

Q11-how many hours you spend on watching Streaming videos on daily basis?
 125 responses

57 out of 125 respondents spend 0-2 hours on watching streaming videos on daily basis,37 respondents spend 2-4

hours,22 respondents spend 4-6 hours and 9 respondents spend 6-8 hours.

Q12- what is your frequency of watching Streaming videos?
 125 responses

45 respondents out of 125 watch Streaming Videos somedays of the week,29 respondents watch once a

week,28 respondents watch per day and 23 respondents watch monthly.

Q13- Rank your acceptance of the content shown in Streaming videos.
 125 responses

For the acceptance of the content shown in the Streaming Videos 44 % of

respondents agree with that,25.6% of respondents neither agree nor

Disagree, 24% of respondents Totally Agree, 4.8% of respondents disagree and 1.6% of respondents are strongly Disagree.

Q14-Do you think content of Streaming videos are more modern/adopting western culture?
 125 responses

41.6% of respondents agree with the statement that the content of Streaming Videos is more modern/adopts western culture, 31.2% of respondents strongly agree, 20.8% of

respondents neither are neither agree nor disagree, 4.8% respondents disagree and 1.6% respondents strongly Disagree.

Q15-What are the determinants due to which you prefer to watch Streaming videos?[rank them 1=Most Preferred, 5=Least Preferred]

The determinants due to which respondents prefer to watch Streaming Videos are Availability which is most

preferred followed by Content, Convenience, time, and cost is the least preferred determinant.

Q16-What do you like most about Streaming videos?
 125 responses

Content (56.8%) is the key factor in Streaming Videos followed by Convenience (48%), Availability (39.2%), Cost (28.8%), and Time (16.8%). (the total percentage is more than 100 % because one respondent responds for more than one option).

Q17-Do you think there should be any change/any suggestion for Streaming videos?

90 Respondents suggest no change for Streaming Videos whereas 35 respondents suggest some changes which are There should be a reduction in the cost of Streaming Videos or free of cost.

- cost of Streaming Videos is a little bit higher side. If they cut off some charges the consumption of streaming videos increases in the J curve.

- Streaming Videos should be AD Free.
- Streaming Videos should be less fictional.
- Streaming Videos should be more motivated.
- In the Indian context, content like good documentaries on business and politics should be promoted (as of now, there is a dearth of documentaries in India).
- It's all about their content. As the content should not be available for all age groups because it does not show all right content but also covers criminal activities, western culture focus more so there must be some age restriction.
- Information regarding their plans is not easy to available in a simple manner. all plans look similar to each other. it is very confusing to choose. improve package information and features, by this change, they will see a huge increment in their viewership.
- "Cinema is the reflection of the society", now this quote should be changed to streaming videos are the true reflection of society because the cinema is becoming commercial day by day, so they are losing the character that we knew, on the other hand, the streaming videos are more realistic and practical, so now they are playing the role of classical cinema in today's world.

Conclusion

The total number of Respondents is 125 which belongs to Agra city of age group 18-35 years. Most of the respondents (86.4%) are aware of the concept of Streaming Videos. 84.8% of respondents like to watch streaming videos, and Amazon Prime (59.2%) is the most preferred Streaming video platform followed by Hotstar (55.2%) and Netflix (53.6%). Comedy (49.6%) is the most preferred content followed by horror (41.6%) and Thriller (40%). Most Favorite series are Mirzapur, The Family Man, Money Heist, and FRIENDS. Streaming Videos affect the behavior of respondents in both positive and negative ways. According to most of the respondents, Streaming Videos are Affordable. Streaming Videos are more Affordable as compared to DTH. Most of the respondents agree with the statement that Streaming Videos are better than T.V. Streaming Videos do have not much economic impact on respondents. Most respondents spent 0-2 hours watching Streaming Videos on daily basis, they watch Streaming Videos sometimes a week. Content of Streaming Videos is Acceptable. Streaming Videos are adapting Western Culture. Availability and

content are the determinants of Streaming Videos. Content and Convenience are the Key Factors in Streaming Videos. Respondents suggest some changes which there should be a reduction in the cost of Streaming Videos or free of cost. "Cinema is the reflection of the society", now this quote should be changed to streaming videos are the true reflection of society because the cinema is becoming commercial day by day, so they are losing the character that we knew, on the other hand, the streaming videos are more realistic and practical, so now they are playing the role of classical cinema in today's world.

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